

PREDICTION OF OBSTETRIC AND PERINATAL COMPLICATIONS IN PREGNANT WOMEN WITH ADENOMYOSIS

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Background. Endometriosis and adenomyosis are among the most common gynecological diseases affecting women of reproductive age. According to global data, endometriosis occurs in approximately 10–15% of women and is associated with infertility, pelvic pain, and adverse pregnancy outcomes. Adenomyosis may significantly affect implantation processes, placental development, and the course of pregnancy, leading to an increased risk of obstetric and perinatal complications.

Objective. To evaluate the role of adenomyosis in the development of obstetric and perinatal complications and to determine prognostic markers for adverse pregnancy outcomes.

Materials and Methods. The study included 103 women aged 25–35 years with different forms of adenomyosis who were examined at the clinical bases of the Tashkent Medical Academy between 2021 and 2025. Clinical, instrumental, biochemical, morphological, and statistical research methods were used. Particular attention was paid to the assessment of trophoblastic β -1-glycoprotein levels in maternal blood serum as a potential predictor of pregnancy complications.

Results. The results demonstrated that obstetric and perinatal complications occurred in 62.1% of pregnant women with adenomyosis. The most common complications included spontaneous miscarriage, placental dysfunction, hypertensive disorders, fetal growth restriction, and preterm birth. The risk of spontaneous miscarriage was significantly increased (OR=2.8; RR=2.4), while the risk of early and very early preterm birth was markedly elevated (OR=17.5; RR=15.6). In addition, increased risks were identified for placental dysfunction

(OR=2.9; RR=2.4), hypertensive disorders (OR=3.1; RR=2.5), fetal growth restriction (OR=5.7; RR=5.6), placenta previa (OR=3.1; RR=2.7), and abnormal placental attachment (OR=4.0; RR=3.5).

A significant relationship was identified between decreased levels of trophoblastic β -1-glycoprotein in maternal serum and the development of pregnancy complications. When the level of this biomarker was reduced twofold compared with standard values, the risk of miscarriage and placental dysfunction increased. A 2.3-fold decrease was associated with preeclampsia and fetal growth restriction, while a 5.3-fold decrease significantly increased the risk of very early preterm birth.

The use of комплекс therapy including dienogest-containing combined oral contraceptives and indole-3-carbinol for pre-pregnancy preparation significantly improved reproductive outcomes, increasing the pregnancy rate by 1.8 times (64.1%) and reducing obstetric complications.

Conclusion. Adenomyosis significantly increases the risk of obstetric and perinatal complications. Decreased levels of trophoblastic β -1-glycoprotein can serve as an important prognostic biomarker for predicting adverse pregnancy outcomes. Early diagnosis and комплекс preventive management may improve pregnancy outcomes in women with adenomyosis.

